

SYSTEMATIC PREDICTIVE PERMEABILITY MODELLING USING COMMERCIAL CFD AND DEDICATED CALCULATION METHOD

F. Robitaille, C.C. Wong, A.C. Long, C.D. Rudd

*School of Mechanical, Materials, Manufacturing Engineering & Management
University of Nottingham, University Park, Nottingham NG7 2RD, U.K.*

ABSTRACT

This paper presents initial systematic validation work performed for the ‘stream-surface’ permeability calculation method. The context of the work and the diverse operations involved are discussed. The paper begins with the identification of the key requirements for the method in a context of industrial filling simulations performed in support of the development of industrial RTM processing operations and of the design of composite parts based on textile reinforcements. The implementation of the method is discussed as well as its integration with the textile modelling software developed by the authors. Then the systematic validation of the stream-surface method is covered. The validation has two aspects: a computational one where the results of this fast but simplified numerical method are compared to those of slower but more rigorous CFD-based methods, and an experimental one where predicted permeability values are compared to measured ones. This paper covers initial work related to the former aspect only. In order to build confidence in the method, validation work must be conducted systematically and thoroughly starting from the simple 2D cases presented here. Systematic planning of the simulation work to be conducted for validation purposes is introduced.

Whilst the paper presents early results, initial comparative validations are promising. The stream-surface has a tendency to underestimate permeability values by approximately 7% on average when compared to CFD. This difference is dwarfed by the amplitude of the effect of changes in the different geometric parameters that were varied in producing the results presented here. Trends in permeability values predicted by both methods are very similar.

KEYWORDS: unit cell, permeability, prediction, validation

NOMENCLATURE

Variables

a	Aspect ratio	v	Fluid velocity (m/s)
h	Height (m)	vf	Fibre volume fraction
K	Permeability (m ²)	w	width
n	Power, in tow shape definition	μ	Fluid viscosity (Pa.s)
P	Pressure (Pa)		

Subscripts

c	Cell
d	Flow domain
l	Local value
t	Tow

INTRODUCTION

Simulation software for the filling of resin transfer (RTM) moulds has been available commercially for a number of years and is now used routinely to assist RTM mould design; LIMS™ and PAM-RTM™ are the most widespread examples. In order to make the software more useful a number of practical aspects were considered by developers and other researchers over the years. Examples include the automated positioning of gates and vents, the permeability of preforms in corners, thickness changes and everywhere they deviate from the basic flat, constant thickness case, and others. These practical aspects are reviewed in [1]. The incorporation of statistical permeability data in stochastic analyses of the filling where a number of simulations are performed in order to evaluate the robustness of a manufacturing operation is ongoing. This capability is being integrated in filling simulation software, and it is assumed that the required permeability data is available.

Despite the important advances mentioned above, most industrial usage of filling simulation software still consists in locating gates, runners and vents for a given part geometry. Typically a process engineer is asked to develop a robust manufacturing operation for a part of stated geometry. At best, the interaction between part designer and process engineer will cover minor changes in the geometry such as corner radii, release angles, etc. but the engineer generally has no further role in defining the part geometry. The effects of the combination of reinforcements selected when specifying the preform and of the levels of deformation to which they are subjected on flow rarely influence this selection; in the best circumstances they are evaluated partially. Paradoxically, if filling problems occur at a later stage these will usually be alleviated either by removing reinforcement layers locally, by altering the sealing of the tool, or by re-machining the tool in a remedial and approximate way. The statistical nature of the reinforcements and the subsequent effect on permeability data are usually overlooked.

The cause of this lies in the generation of permeability data. Local permeability tensors, which vary with the combination of reinforcements, mould thickness, compaction and in-plane shear present at each point of the part are either evaluated experimentally or calculated using semi-analytical models. In the former case there is a practical limit to the number of permeability measurements that a process engineer will conduct before running simulations. Such tests are time-consuming and it is widely acknowledged that permeability data obtained from the most rigorous experimental procedure will be scattered, increasing the number of measurements required to obtain acceptable levels of confidence. Experimental permeability data is usually too coarse to take full advantage of filling software.

In the latter case, modelled permeability data will only vary with the local orientation, shear angle and local fibre volume fraction of the preform. Current models [2-4] require or assume principal directions for local permeability tensors whilst in fact these should be determined. The models do not process comprehensive definitions of the reinforcement's architecture or practical geometric artefacts such as nesting, changes in tow sections, wavy tows, or any statistical imperfection. Semi-analytical models provide continuous functions expressing the permeability at each point of a part but these functions are based on macro-scale quantities and bear little relation with the actual meso-scale geometry of the preform, which should be used for permeability calculation. Whatever the means used, generating refined and reliable permeability data is a major task. Iterating part geometry and reinforcement selection in order to account for effected changes in local permeability tensors and in their statistical distribution in a context of stochastic analysis and process robustness is beyond current possibilities.

In order to alleviate this central problem the authors have developed a general computational method for permeability prediction, the 'stream-surface method'. The stream-surface method is described briefly in the next section. In order to be of practical use the method should apply to virtually any textile preform and be faster than a typical mould filling simulation. This paper discusses the current status and ongoing work on the implementation and validation of the stream-surface method.

The first step in implementing the method consisted in writing software producing geometric models of actual preforms at the meso scale, to be used as domains for permeability calculation [5]. One can

easily show that the notion of periodicity associated with single textile layers breaks down for preforms made of two or more layers oriented arbitrarily, even before any statistical imperfection is introduced. The question of domain extents for permeability calculation remains open but as a general rule a domain should cover a few unit cells of a given textile. The author's software builds volumes representing the tows within a domain as well as the empty volumes extending between these tows and presents these volumes in a predictable and consistent way, following precise criteria (Fig. 1).

The second step consisted in implementing the actual stream-surface method. This implementation work is ongoing; basic stream-surface software is operational and was used to generate some of the data presented in this paper. Current work consists in developing the interface between the stream-surface software and the textile modelling software.

The third step, and last before fully-fledged application of the method, is validation. Two distinct types of validation must be conducted: numerical and experimental. The stream-surface method is fast by design; this is achieved by simplifying the problem through a number of hypotheses. There is a need to validate these hypotheses by comparing predicted permeability values to those obtained from more rigorous methods i.e. the Navier-Stokes equations. In order to gain confidence in the stream-surface method such numerical validation must be conducted systematically, starting from simple cases. This paper presents such validation results. After numerical validation the method can be validated experimentally by comparing its predictions to measured values. The main consideration here is the accuracy of the meso-scale geometric model. In calculating permeability at the meso-scale one needs either to obtain proper local geometric information at that scale, or to conduct stochastic calculations. Practical sense dictates the latter, reinforcing the need for a fast method and underlining the importance of just hypotheses in its development.

Figure 1. Geometric models of textiles and volumes surrounding them, to be used for permeability calculation. Left: unit-cell, plain weave; Centre: plan view ($-1.5 < x < 8$, $-1.5 < y < 8$); Right: Outlines of basic empty volumes for flow calculation over domain $2 < x < 7$, $2 < y < 7$.

CALCULATION METHODS

The stream-surface method for permeability calculation was presented in a number of publications [1,6,7]; its principles and hypotheses are briefly reviewed here. The computational technique used for validation calculations is also described. This description is presented after the problem statement in order to introduce the full computational problem. Then the stream-surface method is reviewed with an emphasis on the simplifications made in its development.

The aim is to obtain the components of the in-plane permeability tensor at any given point [8,9]. Typically this is done by generating 3 values of the directional permeability over a 3D domain of some extent, representing part of a preform (Fig. 2a). Consider a brick-shaped domain (all adjacent faces normal to each other) where an in-plane pressure difference is imposed between two opposite

faces. If the velocity field is known one can obtain a directional permeability for the complete domain K_d , say along x , by specifying the pressure gradient and velocity as independent variables in Darcy's law (Eqn. 1a) applied to the domain. The velocity, or volume flow rate per unit area, can be obtained on any section normal to the pressure gradient. If the velocity field is unknown it can be derived from the pressure field, specifying the local pressure gradient and local directional permeability K_l as independent variables in Darcy's law (Eqn. 1b) applied to a part of the domain where a local permeability can be obtained. This can be done over normal sections that are entirely porous using models by Gebart [10] or Brusckhe and Advani [11], or over sections that are entirely empty using the Hagen-Poiseuille relation [12] for flow between two infinite plaques, with $K_l = h^2/12$ [10].

$$K_d = \left| v \mu \frac{dx}{dP} \right| \quad (1a)$$

$$v = -\frac{K_l}{\mu} \cdot \frac{dP}{dx} \quad (1b)$$

The same ideas apply to 2D domains (Fig. 2b). Pressure fields, velocity fields and permeability values can be obtained in the same way. Whilst 2D calculations reduce computational effort they assume that preforms have identical sections everywhere and that flow components normal to the 2D domain are negligible. Such calculations are of limited use in predicting the permeability of actual preforms but they constitute an ideal first step in validating the stream-surface method. Initial validation results presented in this paper were obtained for 2D domains.

Figure 2. Geometry, boundary conditions, pressure and velocity fields; a) 3D case, b) 2D case.

The stream-surface method consists essentially in reducing the dimension of the calculation domain, in the first case from a volume (3D) to a multi-faceted interconnected curved surface (2.5D), and in the second case from a surface (2D) to a multi-branched interconnected curve (1.5D).

Validation calculations in 2D and 3D are conducted using the CFD software FluentTM. Starting from tow sections enclosed in a rectangular domain or tow volumes enclosed in brick-shaped domains, the porosity and permeability of the tows are specified along with the density and viscosity of the fluid. A pressure difference is imposed between two opposed faces. No-slip boundary conditions are specified on the walls. Isothermal continuity and momentum equations are solved in steady state laminar flow over the saturated domain. A directional permeability is calculated from Darcy's law (Eqn. 1a) using velocity defined as the volume flow rate divided by the entire cross-section area in 3D or their equivalent per unit width in 2D. As this paper presents initial validation results in 2D the porous tows were not included (Fig. 3). For the cases presented it can be shown that tow permeability does not affect preform permeability. The stream-surface method covers flow through porous tows; its effect will be investigated systematically in future work. All 2D meshes had more than 10 000 elements.

Figure 3. Pressure and velocity fields for 2D permeability calculation, generated using FluentTM (flow from left to right). a) red: high pressure, blue: low pressure; b) red: high velocity, blue: low velocity.

The 1.5D stream-surface calculations presented in this paper proceed as follows. Starting from a 2D domain (Fig. 4a) the horizontally outermost points of tow sections are used to generate vertical lines that split the domain in a series of basic surfaces (basic empty volumes in 3D), each corresponding to an empty sub-domain (Fig. 4b). A curve is drawn at mid height of each basic surface (Fig. 4c). A number of nodes are then created along these lines (Fig. 4d). The height of the basic surface at each node is used to calculate a local permeability K_l , following [10]. A finite difference mesh is created by joining adjacent nodes, noting that the fluid pressure is equal at any two nodes that are superimposed vertically and lie on the boundaries of the same basic surface. A pressure value is obtained at each node, amplitudes of the local velocities at these points are obtained using Eqn. 1b, and a value of the directional permeability is obtained from Eqn. 1a. In the case illustrated in Fig. 4 no stream-lines are drawn through the tow as it is surrounded by basic surfaces on all sides; in this case flow through the tow is negligible. However the method as described in [1,6,7] does consider flow through tows and through the empty surfaces (or volumes in 3D) defined between the tows. Also the method is developed for 2.5D domains hence its name ‘stream-surface’, as opposed to ‘stream-line’. All stream-surface FD meshes used in this study featured 107 nodes.

Figure 4. Schematic illustration of the stream-surface method for the cases reported in this paper; a) initial domain, b) vertical projection, c) stream-lines, d) nodes for finite difference mesh.

SIMULATION PLANNING

A systematic comparative evaluation of the above methods (1.5D stream-surface vs. 2D CFD) has been undertaken. In preparing this evaluation,

- 1) A number of independent geometric parameters were identified; by modifying their value a large array of meso-scale flow domains representing parts of actual preforms can be created.
- 2) In each simulation the values taken by these parameters are selected with the purpose of highlighting their individual effects from minimal computational effort.

The long-term aim of this work consists in documenting the effect of all parameters used in defining any domain from a full 3D multi-layer preform, and to compare the behaviour of different calculation

methods in all circumstances. The systematic way to proceed towards this aim is to start with single tow sections in 2D, progress to multiple tow sections forming single textile layers, and on to multiple tow sections forming multiple textile layers. Conclusions from the 2D work will form a basis from which systematic 3D work will be initiated for single textile layers, and finally for superimposed ones.

Taguchi [13] planning is being used throughout the work. Groups of simulations where only one parameter is varied are also conducted for illustration purposes. Information provided by both types of plans appears in this paper which presents our initial validation work on single tow sections in 2D. The first task consisted in identifying suitable independent geometric parameters. Before discussing them 3 notes are made:

- a) A nominal geometric case was created to separate geometric effects from scale effects. The nominal geometric case will be defined as geometric parameters are introduced.
- b) Geometric parameters were selected on the basis of independence with due consideration to practical reality. For example, the cell fibre volume fraction ν_f^c (equal to the local fibre volume fraction of the composite) is a parameter as it can be controlled. On the contrary the tow fibre volume fraction ν_f^t is not a parameter because in practice one changes the amount of fibres placed in the tool; this latter parameter was selected instead.
- c) The parameters defining the tow section were identified first. The parameters defining the cell were identified afterwards. The latter are independent but they are expressed as functions of the former to alleviate scale effects.

The nominal geometric case has a width $w_t = 5$ mm. The nominal width stays constant to address scale effects. However, the width of tows generated for the different cases presented in this paper does vary, with the tow aspect ratio for example. The tow aspect ratio (width/height) a_t is parameter **P1**, with a nominal aspect ratio $a_t = 5$. The section is defined by the equation of a generalised ellipse:

$$y = \pm \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{a_t^2} \right)^n \quad (2)$$

The tow width w_t and height h_t are defined along x and y respectively. The power n , which is parameter **P2**, affects the general shape of the tow with $n = 0.5$ corresponding to an ellipse and $n < 0.5$ evolving towards a fuller, more rectangular shape; $n = 0.3$ for the nominal case. In all cases presented here the 4 quadrants of the section are symmetric. The nominal case contains 10 000 fibres of diameter $15.8 \mu\text{m}$; these numbers were selected from the author's practice. The number of fibres in a tow, indicative of the quantity of glass, was kept constant here as it does not affect flow. Parameters **P1** and **P2** fully define the tow shape and its fibre volume fraction ν_f^t . Values selected for each parameter appear in Table 1.

The composite unit cell is defined as follows. The minimum dimensions for the rectangular flow domain (Fig. 4) are the tow width w_t and tow height h_t . From these a maximum value for the fibre volume fraction of the cell (or composite) $\nu_{f,c,max}$ can be obtained. Parameter **P3** is the fibre volume fraction of the cell ν_f^c ; selected values are multiples of $\nu_{f,c,max}$ as shown in Table 1. To a given value of $\nu_{f,c,max}$ corresponds an area for the rectangular flow domain. The aspect ratio of the domain is the last parameter **P4** included in this study. Values are selected between the minimum and maximum limits made possible by the fibre volume fraction of the cell **P3** and the aspect ratio of the tow **P1**.

The 17 combinations of parameters **P1**, **P2**, **P3** and **P4** selected for this study appear in Table 1. Further work is planned for single tows in 2D where the tow section is not symmetric, it touches the domain boundaries, and it is not located at the centre of the domain. Further work on single tows will also include flow through the porous tow. Conclusions from this work will be used in defining further 2D work for tow sections assembled in single and multiple layers.

Table 1. Parameters and results of 1.5D stream-surface and 2D Fluent™ simulations.

Simulation	Parameters				Results: Permeability (m ²)	
	Tow aspect ratio	Section shape power	Cell fibre vol. fraction	Cell aspect ratio	1.5D stream-surface	2D Fluent™
	a_t	n	vf_c	a_c		
P1	P2	P3	P4			
1 (nominal)	5	0.3	0.80 $vf_{c,max}$	5	9.63×10^{-11}	10.20×10^{-11}
2	3	0.3	0.80 $vf_{c,max}$	3	16.10×10^{-11}	16.80×10^{-11}
3	4	0.3	0.80 $vf_{c,max}$	4	12.00×10^{-11}	12.80×10^{-11}
4	6	0.3	0.80 $vf_{c,max}$	6	8.03×10^{-11}	8.71×10^{-11}
5	7	0.3	0.80 $vf_{c,max}$	7	6.88×10^{-11}	8.18×10^{-11}
6	5	0.1	0.80 $vf_{c,max}$	5	6.38×10^{-11}	6.67×10^{-11}
7	5	0.2	0.80 $vf_{c,max}$	5	8.20×10^{-11}	8.76×10^{-11}
8	5	0.4	0.80 $vf_{c,max}$	5	10.90×10^{-11}	11.60×10^{-11}
9	5	0.5	0.80 $vf_{c,max}$	5	12.00×10^{-11}	13.00×10^{-11}
10	5	0.3	0.70 $vf_{c,max}$	5	33.10×10^{-11}	36.50×10^{-11}
11	5	0.3	0.75 $vf_{c,max}$	5	18.70×10^{-11}	20.20×10^{-11}
12	5	0.3	0.85 $vf_{c,max}$	5	4.23×10^{-11}	4.54×10^{-11}
13	5	0.3	0.90 $vf_{c,max}$	5	1.38×10^{-11}	1.61×10^{-11}
14	5	0.3	0.80 $vf_{c,max}$	4.5000	26.50×10^{-11}	26.20×10^{-11}
15	5	0.3	0.80 $vf_{c,max}$	4.7500	16.60×10^{-11}	17.00×10^{-11}
16	5	0.3	0.80 $vf_{c,max}$	5.3125	4.23×10^{-11}	4.89×10^{-11}
17	5	0.3	0.80 $vf_{c,max}$	5.6250	1.38×10^{-11}	1.81×10^{-11}

RESULTS

The effect of parameter **P1**(tow aspect ratio) on permeability appears in Fig. 5 for both calculation methods. The black and red curves represent permeability values obtained from the stream-surface method in 1.5D and from Fluent™ in 2D, respectively. The numbers next to each point identify the cases as specified in Table 1. The geometry of each case is also shown to the right of the figure, with points from left to right on the curves corresponding to geometries from top to bottom of the pile. The actual values taken by the studied parameter, here the tow aspect ratio, appear on the horizontal axis of the curve. Similar results appear in Figs. 6, 7 and 8 for parameters **P2**, **P3** and **P4** respectively.

Figure 5. Effect of the tow aspect ratio on permeability.

Figure 6. Effect of the section shape power on permeability.

Figure 7. Effect of the cell volume fraction on permeability.

Figure 8. Effect of the cell aspect ratio on permeability.

Fig. 5 shows that the permeability decreases when the aspect ratio of the tow increases; the cross-sectional area of the tow and cell are constant for the 5 cases presented (cases 1 to 5). The reduction in permeability is due to a reduction in the height and an elongation of the 2 empty channels defined between the tow and the horizontal boundaries of the domain. Height values are 76 μm (case 2), 66 μm (case 3), 59 μm (case 1 – nominal), 54 μm (case 4) and 50 μm (case 5).

Fig. 6 shows that the permeability increases when the power n increases (Eqn. 2). Higher values of n correspond to an elliptical section whilst lower values correspond to sections that are closer to a rectangle; the right part of the figure shows domains of increasing n , from top to bottom. The increase in permeability is mostly due to a reduction in the length of the more constricted part of the channels.

The amplitude of the effect of parameters **P1** and **P2** on permeability is similar. Fig. 7 shows that the cell fibre volume fraction, parameter **P3**, has a significantly stronger effect on the permeability. Again the permeability is reduced when the height of the empty channels decreases. Whilst the effect of the tow aspect ratio is relatively light as all vertical dimensions stay proportional when **P1** is varied (Fig. 5), here the dimensions of the tow stay constant for the 5 cases presented (cases 10, 11, 1, 12, 13). The effect of the change in cell fibre volume fraction on the channel height is therefore much more direct.

The effect of parameter **P4** is also strong, for the same reasons. The dimensions of the tows are identical for all cases presented in Fig. 8 (cases 14, 15, 1, 16, 17) and the section area of the domain also remains constant. Therefore, any change in the cell aspect ratio has a major effect on the height of the empty channels.

The curves presented in Figs. 5 to 8 show that predicted permeability values are of the right magnitude and that results obtained from both methods in the same conditions are in good agreement; the same trends are predicted in both cases. At this stage this aspect is more important than the relative amplitude of the effects of parameters **P1**, **P2**, **P3** and **P4** on the permeability. Whilst early observations about the importance of heterogeneity in textile preforms may begin to emerge, it is essential to obtain positive results on the computational aspect of the problem from the start. The stream-surface method is inherently faster than any standard solution (less than 2 seconds vs. 2 to 3 minutes for the cases presented here) and it also alleviates practical difficulties associated with the meshing of intricate domains. But clearly, the approximate permeability values that it provides must be reasonably good. The results presented here are very encouraging in that regard.

DISCUSSION

The information presented above constitutes early results. For example, Fig. 7 shows that the permeability varies by one order of magnitude when the cell fibre volume fraction vf_c varies between 70% to 90% of its maximum possible value $vf_{c,max}$. Here $vf_{c,max}$ is 39.3% hence vf_c varies between 27.3% and 35.3%. One could argue, with reason, that the effect of this parameter (**P3**) is unlikely to be so great in practice. Generally speaking the stream-surface method seems to be very sensitive to variations in geometric parameters. These strong effects are a consequence of having flow in empty channels only for the cases presented here. High velocities develop in the constricted sections of these channels as shown in Fig. 3. Such empty channels are bound to have a lesser effect when more complex - and realistic - geometries are considered. Besides, it is generally acknowledged that heterogeneity and inter-tow channels in textile reinforcements are important to resin flow. Textile reinforcements for RTM have been designed specifically with this in mind.

A number of aspects of the stream-surface method require more attention. Among these is the fact that resin cannot flow vertically to and from tow volumes. Pressure distributions observed where stream-lines/stream-surfaces connect and resin flow is split by tows also need special consideration. At this early stage these issues do not seem to affect the performance of the method for fairly thin preforms where relatively little flow occurs through the thickness. The ongoing computational validation will

cover such aspects. As the cases considered progressively become more complex and closer to the reality it is expected that the method will provide permeability values that are closer to those observed experimentally. At this stage it will be possible to evaluate the effect of practical aspects such as the effect of the fibre architecture and its imperfections, and to use predicted values of the permeability in conjunction with mould filling simulation software.

One should note that the stream-surface method can be solved using mould filling simulation software, although at a cost in time. Eventually it will be possible to use the same software to calculate local permeability values and to simulate the filling of RTM moulds.

CONCLUSIONS

Initial validation results for the stream-surface method for permeability prediction were presented. The cases considered are single tows defined in 2D with no porous zones. The results show that the 1.5D stream-surface method provides very similar results to 2D CFD. For the cases presented here the average error on permeability was 7% whilst CPU times were cut by approximately 100 times. Computational validation of the method is ongoing, and will be followed by experimental validation at a later stage.

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